

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: VAN HERWAARDE****FIRST NAME: ELIAS****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11%

The author used the following software: (MSWORD 2021 on Mac)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. When completing any academic writing, why is it imperative to utilise a style guide in your writing and ensure strict conformity?
 - This will ensure that your writing is consistent and follows a standard throughout, including structure, naming, and referencing.**¹
 - This will ensure that you receive the highest marks possible in your assignments for your course.
 - It will ensure a logical flow to your work.
 - It will make it easier for you to know how to write your work.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*: Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Ninth edition (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 14.

2. In academic writing, it is essential that the author ensures that the work they have produced is optimised as much as possible to allow ease of reading and ensure the reader fully understands the message being portrayed; what are some of the ways that the author can increase the optimisation of the paper?

Focus on the first seven or eight words of a sentence, ensure perfect grammar and punctuation, and ensure that the title clearly conveys the nature of the paper.²

Edit your work to ensure that there are no spelling or grammatical errors.

Read your work several times and make edits to ensure that it is easy to understand and it flows.

Have someone else review your work to ensure it is of a high standard.

3. What are the key standards that a rule of style will outline?

The research topic, drafting your paper, grammar, citations and tables and figures.³

Commas, spelling, numbers, and place names.

Literature review, data analysis and conclusion.

Title, grammar, data analysis and conclusion.

² Turabian, 118–29.

³ Ibid.

4. When utilising Zotero for reference management, what are the key areas that the user must be fully aware of and monitor to ensure correct references to a high standard?
- Inserting the correct meta data into the relevant fields in the Zotero application and reviewing the produced reference for conformity.⁴**
 - Once a reference is produced, edit it as required to ensure it conforms to the required standards.
 - You don't need to edit or review the references, as they are always produced correctly.
 - Insert the references from the Zotero app and then re-edit them by using a style guide.
5. What of the following scenarios is referencing not required?
- When discussing a topic that is considered to be general knowledge.⁵**
 - When you have already discussed this topic in your work in a separate section.
 - If the topic that you are discussing is only from secondary literature and you can not find the primary source.
 - When you are discussing the news.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck de Kiev, Director. *Zotero Training 2*. EUCLID University, 2016.

⁵ Turabian, 370–80.

6. When considering research methods, what method is where the researcher seeks to understand the thoughts of a group of people?

- Ethnography.**⁶
- Grounded theory.
- Interpretivism.
- Phenomenology.

7. A dissertation title is an essential piece and must rapidly and clearly show the reader what the dissertation is about; when is the best time to formulate a title for your dissertation?

- Have a rough title to start, but decide on the final title at the end once the dissertation is complete.**⁷
- The first thing you do should be to decide on your title.
- Do not decide on your title until the end of writing your dissertation.
- There is no best time to make the title, and you can do as you please.

8. When identifying a qualitative research problem for your study, what is the best way to think about formulating this?

- Finding an area with incomplete knowledge on an issue.**⁸

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 165.

⁷ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 31.

⁸ Sampson, 28.

- Choosing a subject that you are interested in.
 - Undertake a literature review before thinking about your subject.
 - Think of a hypothesis about a subject and then how to test the theory.
9. When considering the main components of a dissertation, they would be;
- Title, introduction, literature review, methodology, data, findings, conclusions, and recommendations.**⁹
 - Introduction, main body, and conclusion.
 - Literature review, search strategy, methods, and recommendations.
 - Title, methodology, findings, and conclusion.
10. In research, the methodology used depends on the type of problem and purpose; what are the main differences between quantitative and qualitative research?
- Qualitative research is aimed at developing a hypothesis about a problem, and quantitative research uses numerical data to explain a phenomenon.**¹⁰
 - Qualitative research is about theory, whereas quantitative research is numerical.
 - Qualitative research is based on phenomenology, and quantitative research tests a hypothesis.
 - Quantitative research is statistical and qualitative is based on theory.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 299–529.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 135.

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